

Ecozona30: rammed earth and digital fabrication for urban regeneration

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Abstract

Urban life is now beginning to emit the first signs of regeneration at a time of covid-19 pandemic; this calls for municipal public organs to urgently mitigate the effects of social isolation through the redesign of urban spaces. To this goal, in Belo Horizonte, Brazil, the Municipality, in partnership with German partners Wuppertal, GIZ and TUMI, and other local organisations, implemented an intervention entitled "Zone 30", that foresees the establishment of local roads with a maximum speed of 30km/h for vehicles, giving priority to those who walk, cycle or have reduced mobility. Being part of the Fab City Belo Horizonte network, BHTrans, invited the Fab City members Fab Lab Newton and StudioN to develop the sustainable urban furniture for an intervention area of "Zone30". With the challenge of using local material, furniture was developed in rammed earth, an ancient vernacular construction technique. The formwork was developed with an innovative locking system that reuses the residues of wood plywood which had been CNC-cut, thus excluding the use of metallic locks and facilitating the process of execution. The results are sustainable furniture made with local soil and with a construction technique easy to be reapplied in different locations.

Keywords

Sustainable Urban Mobility, urban planning, rammed earth, FabLab.

1 Introduction

Urban life is now beginning to emit the first signs of regeneration at a time when the covid-19 pandemic is being combated worldwide through vaccination on a global scale. This calls for municipal public organs to urgently mitigate the effects of social isolation through the redesign of urban spaces, addressing the population needs of this "new normal".

But for the citizens of Belo Horizonte, capital of Minas Gerais state and the sixth biggest city in Brazil, regenerating the city has been an important goal in the last six decades. The capital was the first planned city of Brazil, and it was built 123 years ago as a symbol for brazilian urban planning modernity, prioritising the construction of roads in a time when automobiles represented the evolution of mobility. But in the

1960s, due to expansion of the city, the tremendous growth of the automobile fleet forced the City Hall to review its master plan, in order to revert the consequences of the traffic in the quality of life of its citizens. That's when the human dimension has arisen as an important factor to rethink the streets and the public space (URBAN PATHWAYS, 2020).

In 2010, The Municipality of Belo Horizonte, through the Transport and Transit Public Enterprise - BHTrans - and under the leadership of Eveline Trevisan, Sustainability and Environment Coordinator, launched the first version of Belo Horizonte's Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan, named PlanMob-BH. Since then, PlanMob-BH has become an important instrument to guide mobility actions, prioritising public transportation, walking and cycling and proposing restrictions to individual motorized displacement (URBAN PATHWAYS, 2020)

As part of this long-term strategy for sustainable mobility called PlanMob-BH, in 2014 the Belo Horizonte Municipality, in partnership with German partners Wuppertal Institute (German Research Institute), UN-Habitat, WRI Brasil (International Research Institute), and other local organisations like Nossa BH (local NGO) and Fab Lab Newton (academic Fab Lab of Newton University Center), implemented an intervention entitled "Zone 30". This diversity of stakeholders - from international organisations with extensive experience in such projects to civil society groups and an university - was an essential factor for the success of the project, gathering not only technical background but assuring that the community needs were heard and the local residents co-created all the intervention.

The 'Zone 30' foresees the establishment of local roads with a maximum speed of 30km/h for vehicles, giving priority to those who walk, cycle or have reduced mobility, especially the elderly and children. The initiative is the result of the demands claimed by cyclists' associations, but discussions with the local community allowed the municipality to conclude that 'Zone 30' areas favours all city dwellers, transforming areas to become much safer for pedestrians. In 2019, the first 'Zone 30' intervention area was implemented around schools in the Cachoeirinha neighbourhood, located in the northeast region of the city. The initiative had a very positive impact on the local community and became a permanent intervention. In the same year another 'Zone 30' was launched, replicating the success at the Confisco neighbourhood, located in the northern area of the city.

In 2020, using the same methodology process, the stakeholders implemented the third 'Zone 30' intervention, located in the Santa Tereza neighbourhood.

The current process of transforming public space in contemporary cities is not static. The uses and physical needs of spaces have been evolving in an attempt to keep up with the urgency of the ephemeral, which is one of the aspects of post-modernity. We face urban political, social, economic, and environmental changes that increasingly need speed and instant response. The complexity of urban problems does not always allow processes to be resolved instantly, but it is undeniable that the speed and power of technological advances simplified communication between different social actors and facilitated decision-making processes. Ecozone is an example of the development of contemporary urbanism: a quick response, the result of a joint effort to reformulate a space that could be physically improved to meet the current demand of users for quality public space.

Through a participatory and collaborative decision-making process, nearby residents were able to give their opinion and dynamically act in the spatial reconfiguration of the Joaquim Ferreira da Luz Square in order to put neighbors, merchants, and patrons of the place in contact and empower them in view of the decisions taken in dialogue with the government, NGOs, partner entities, and financing institutions.

Being part of the Fab City Belo Horizonte network, BHTrans invited the Fab City members Fab Lab Newton and StudioN (academic Fab Lab and school office of the Architecture and Urbanism course of the University Center Newton Paiva, respectively) to develop the sustainable urban furniture for an intervention area of "Zone30". With the challenge of using local material, furniture was developed in rammed earth, an ancient vernacular earth construction technique.

Architecture, or earth construction technique, is the generic designation given to building materials produced with the earth without going through the burning process (Oliveira, 2005), which is one of these techniques for adobe production.

The use of land as a building material is one of the oldest techniques used by man. Even today, in various regions of the globe, the earth is used in the construction of houses, translating the identity, history and culture of various populations.

The formwork, designed by Studio N and produced in the Fab Lab Newton, was developed with an innovative locking system that reuses the residues of wood plywood which had been CNC-cut, thus excluding the use of metallic locks and facilitating the process of assembly and disassembly during the execution.

This article aims to report the development process of this urban furniture and the results obtained for the Zona30 project in the Santa Tereza neighbourhood, where the use of the millenary technique of "taipa de pilão", combined with the optimization of processes provided by digital fabrication, give rise to a handmade-digital process in which design, tradition and technology play the role of creating sustainable spaces for the regeneration of life in cities.

2 The Concept

As said by Albert Einstein, "we cannot solve our problems with the same thinking we used when we created them". Providing sustainable urban development is not only about applying technical and political strategies.

Only with a change of mindset is it possible to build a new ecosystem with more creative, ecological and proactive ways to identify and solve the local problems. In this scenario, the participation of the local citizens plays a huge role, by using participatory methodologies to increase their support in all stages of the project. Co-creative initiatives with neighbours empower them to have an impact and change their community, as well as raise awareness and increase the collective knowledge on sustainable urban development and environmental issues.

Santa Tereza is one of the first neighborhoods of the city, being part of its construction in 1890. However, its origin comes from irregular occupation. Despite being adjacent to the central region, the zone suffers from lack of conditions of mobility and accessibility, with low coverage of public transport.

But thanks to the plain streets that bring a great presence of cyclists, and walkable distance to public transport options, Santa Tereza is known by its great potential to have a very engaged community, thanks to the cultural scene, with a large presence of restaurants, cultural centres and a lively nightlife.

For Santa Tereza, the original plan was to implement Zone 30 in the surroundings of schools, repeating the location criteria used for *Cachoeirinha* and *Confisco*. But due to the closing schools during the pandemic of covid-19, the intervention was shifted to identify an area for implementing active mobility measures that contributes to the mitigation of lockdown consequences and the recovery of local economy.

3 The Intervention

Zona30 for Santa Tereza has two ways for intervention: the accessibility and permanent open street. For the first one, it was created a bicycle lane of approximately 1.1 km, connecting the existing cycling infrastructure of one of the city's most important avenues to the main access of the neighborhood. The ending point of the first is where the second intervention begins: the Joaquim Ferreira da Luz Square (cf. Figure 1).

To transform the square into a permanent open street, one side of the square was extended to become a space where people can meet, interact and play in compliance with the COVID-19 restrictions, bringing renovation to the square to be a lively open public space again, allowing people to meet and keep social distance.

For this renovation it was created a series of sustainable physical interventions, that includes:

- - Urban furniture
- - Floor paint
- - Landscaping

Figure 1 - Aerial view from the EcoZona 30 intervention in Santa Tereza.
(Source: image from the author)

3.1 The Architecture Project

The opportunity to make the floor-cement furniture in situ made it possible to suggest positions for benches and tables in shaded places and desired by the community. In this sense, places were suggested for the elderly to rest and socialize, benches for adults to sit while watching the children, and even a specially placed seat to watch the train pass, which is next to a gate and gives visibility to the surface subway line adjacent to the intervention, the latter being a very present memory among the inhabitants of the region (cf. Figure 2).

During the three days of the proposal's physical implementation, the opportunity given to volunteers to make the furniture with their own hands and to understand the process involving its elaboration, from the manufacture of molds, the traces of the dough, and use of the rammed earth technique, and cure time promoted intense learning and the possibility of integration between the actors (cf. Figure 3). During the entire physical implementation process, volunteers were able to participate by mixing the materials, sifting the soil, giving opinions on the colors of the layers, preparing the shapes, compacting the mixture, and unmolding the furniture. The appropriation of the street and the understanding and participation in the construction process of the Ecozone allowed the dialogue and action of very different social actors, who coexist and complement the construction of the city in a diversified and essential way.

Figure 2 - Aerial view from the EcoZona 30 intervention in Santa Tereza. (Source: image from the author)

During the meetings, the preliminary project was presented for the community to give their opinion. By listening to their opinions, it was possible to design a project more in line with the needs of the users, such as the bench specially requested to watch the train go by, spaces for the elderly to sit, benches with different heights for children to play and jump, benches and tables positioned in the shade, among others.

Figure 3 - Volunteers at the EcoZona 30 intervention in Santa Tereza. (Source: image from the author)

In the implementation phase, the residents passing by the site soon became interested and stopped to get to know the project. Many parents with children, elderly people walking, adults with their pets, everyone came curious to see and learn about the technique of the mud benches. We heard compliments about the intervention and saw on their faces the happiness in knowing that the space could soon be used by them.

3.2 The Furniture Design

To create quality public spaces for the daily use of the community, people need to have a constant presence and permanence in the local area, thus promoting social interactions. One of the main elements that must be incorporated into the urban environment to promote such permanence and integration is the benches (cf. Figure 4).

Figure 4 - A rammed earth furniture just finished (Source: image from the author)

With the challenge of producing furniture based on the concept of sustainability, with local materials and low environmental impact, benches made of rammed earth were proposed, an ancient and vernacular earth construction technique.

The earth has been one of the construction materials most used by man since prehistory, both in popular constructions and in representative buildings and monuments (Neves & Faria, 2011).

Among the advantages of building with earth in relation to conventional ones is the low energy consumption – associated with an almost zero level of pollution –, which provides efficiency with regard to human health (Torgal & Jalali, 2009).

The rammed earth furniture, in addition to being a sustainable material for using local material, rescues a technique widely used in colonial Brazil, thus enabling the community to have contact with the raw earth and its culture roots.

In this technique, the soil is properly prepared and compacted. Often, some type of binder is added during soil preparation to further improve the structural parameters. In the case in question, soil, a small percentage of cement and a colorant were used to differentiate the layers of compacted earth.

One of the important and complex steps of the rammed earth technique is the elaboration and execution of the formwork. As it is an ancient technique, there are different types of formwork, but they need to be resistant to the impact of the compactor and the pressure exerted by the earth during its compaction, and at the same time they must be light and easy to operate, as the assembly activities and disassembly of forms are crucial for productivity.

As rammed earth is an ancient technique used in the most diverse regions of the world, it is evident that there are different types of shapes and compactors. Forms must be resistant to the impact force of the compactor and the pressure exerted by the earth during its compaction. However, despite being well structured, they must be light and easy to operate, as the activities of assembly and disassembly of the

forms are crucial for productivity (Neves & Faria, 2011). A common way of locking the forms is using metal bars (cf. Figure 5), which, despite being functional, is difficult to assemble and disassemble.

Figure 5: Example of a rammed earth formwork with metal bars locking
(Source: image from the author)

To innovate and make it easier, the shape design was thought so that there would be no metal locking, all fittings are made through cutouts made in 22mm plywood type wood and cut by CNC (cf. Figure 6).

Figure 6: Plywood formwork made with CNC cut in FabLab Newton (Source: image from the author)

Four modules were designed. A 50x50x45 bench (WxLxH), a 100x50x45 bench (WxLxH), a 100x50x75 table (WxLxH) and a module with a movable partition in the center can make a single or double bench or table (cf. Figure 2).

During the execution of the benches, the forms proved to work well, withstanding the pressure of the soil compaction and being quick to assemble and disassemble (cf. Figure 7). Only the form with a central partition that did not present good locking, impairing soil compaction and causing failures in the final product.

Figure 7: Execution of benches using the formworks produced in FabLab Newton
(Source: image from the author)

Due to the pandemic, the community couldn't be invited to participate in the execution, but this is a technique that allows the participation of the community, although necessary the supervise off specialized professional in the area (cf. Figure 8).

Figure 8: Execution of the benches using the moulds produced (Source: image from the author)

The rammed earth benches take an average of one week to dry and harden. Due to the short delivery time, the insulation of the space was not possible, causing small breakages in the furniture. For future deployments, an isolation is recommended to avoid use in the days following the execution, to avoid such breaks.

In the end, 14 modules were executed in 3 working days. This rapid production was only possible thanks to the use of the Fab Lab Newton CNC machine. The benches after drying have good resistance and the space is being well used (cf. Figure 9).

Figure 9: Finished furniture, painting and landscaping (Source: image from the author)

4 Measuring the impact

In order to measure the impact of the interventions, a set of assessments before and after the intervention were created to determine if the results of the activities, which were conducted to increase the safety of pedestrians and cyclists, decrease air and noise pollution, as well as to increase the perception of well-being from the people in the area (cf. Table 1).

Type of Assessment	Description
Mobility & perception survey	On two different days, one before and one after the intervention, a survey was applied to the residents and business owners on the streets surrounding the interventions. The survey included questions about age, gender, mean of transportation, opinion about road safety in the area and other relevant topics. The aim was to understand the different ways in which people in the surroundings commute, but it is also aimed at identifying potential concerns and conflicts in the local population that could lead to resistance against the intervention.
Vehicles, pedestrian and cyclist counts	In addition, during the same days of the survey's application, pedestrian, cyclist and vehicle counts was carried out at two different locations in close proximity to the Square. The data collected about vehicles and pedestrian flows was fundamental to decide upon the areas of intervention and to

Type of Assessment	Description
	see how they changed after the implementation of the project.
Gender audit	The idea of the Gender audit is based on the fact that a large number of women in Brazil refrain from walking, cycling or using public transport due to the insecurity feeling that they have when choosing these transport modes. The gender audit was consisted of several elements. Interviews and focus groups was conducted with women of the Confisco neighbourhood on how they perceive their environment. Several groups was formed to examine the safety and sidewalks conditions at various spots by foot and by bike.
Air and noise quality	In order to quantify the impact of the initiatives implemented in Belo Horizonte, a measuring device for air and noise pollution, a Smart Citizen Kit, was provided by Urban Pathways in 2019. The device was installed a couple of weeks before the project's launch and stayed in the area a couple of weeks after, allowing a comparison before and after the intervention in the PM2.5, PM10 and noise levels.

Table 1: Assesments to measure the impacts of the intervention (Source: Belo Horizonte Municipality)

5 Conclusion

The results are sustainable furniture made with local soil and with a construction technique easy to be reapplied in different locations. These modules were arranged under the shade of a large tree and next to children's play areas. To make the use of the space diverse and spontaneous, different modules of benches and tables were created.

This is an example of how urban regeneration is possible by resignifying millenar techniques through digital fabrication. The use of local raw materials and the participation of the local community from project conception to execution provides a sense of belonging and social empowerment. More than an urban furniture project, this intervention represents the first steps of the integration of the population in the journey of self-sufficiency for Fab City Belo Horizonte.

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References

- Neves, C. & Faria, O. B. (2011). *Técnicas de construção com terra*. Bauru, SP: FEB-UNESP/PROTERR. ISBN 978-85-64472-00-6.
- Oliveira, L. B. D. (2005). *Introdução ao estudo de adobe: construção de alvenaria*. Brasília: Projeto Cantoar/FAU.
- Torgal, F. P. & Jalali, S. (2009) *Construção em Terra: algumas considerações sobre a selecção de solos*. In *Conferência Engenharia* (Vol. 10).
- Urban Pathways, BHTrans, Wuppertal Institut, UN-Habitat, & WRI Brasil. (2020, March). *EcoZona Santa Tereza*. Urban Pathways.

